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Use of the E-beam radiation to diminish the late blowing of cheese

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Running title: E-beam radiation to diminish the late blowing of cheese

21 **Abstract**

22 This study examines the effect of E-beam irradiation on the survival of *Clostridium*
23 *tyrobutyricum* in order to diminish the late blowing of cheese. At dose of 3 kGy brings
24 about a 96% reduction of the *C. tyrobutyricum* spores. This treatment provokes an
25 important reduction in the number of common microbiota presumably composed by
26 lactic acid bacteria. Nevertheless, following reparation of damage, these bacteria still
27 grow to reach almost normal levels. At doses lower than 3 kGy, the changes in physic-
28 chemical and sensory characteristics of the cheese were negligible. An increase of
29 redness (a^* value) and a decrease of yellowness (b^* value) were observed in irradiated
30 samples. The irradiation at dose of 3 kGy had a significant ($P < 0.05$) effect on the
31 texture, decreasing the hardness and increasing the cohesiveness. Although at 3 kGy
32 some changes of appearance, odour and flavour were detected by sensory analysis,
33 samples were adequate for consumption.

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37 **Key words:** *C. tyrobutyricum*, blowing of cheese, clostridia, spores, E-beam

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41 **1. Introduction**

42 Anaerobic spore-formers do not create the problems of the same magnitude in the dairy industry
43 as in the canning industry. However, the importance of anaerobic spore-formers in dairy
44 products must not be overlooked. The late blowing of cheeses is a spoilage caused by the
45 growth of *Clostridium tyrobutyricum* and related species. Usually, the defect does not become
46 noticeable until after a month of ripening, which distinguishes it from coliforms gas, which
47 occurs within 1 - 3 days after manufacturing (Donnelly & Busta, 1981). This is largely due to
48 the butyric fermentation of lactate by those organisms, which yields butyric, and acetic acids,
49 carbon dioxide and hydrogen (Steffen, Flueckiger, Bosset & Ruegg, 1987). Therefore, obvious
50 both off-flavours and off-odours can appear in addition to the gas defect. The products most
51 frequently subject to this are both the long-ripening time cheese made with enzymatic curd and
52 processed cheeses. These types of cheeses are characterized by a very elastic and impermeable
53 texture. Consequently, the gas becomes trapped in the cheese body since it can not diffuse to the
54 outside. The higher the gas accumulation, the greater the pressure, which provokes hole
55 formation and, eventually, the cheese mass to blow. This phenomenon is relatively uncommon
56 if the product is stored under refrigeration because of the mesophilic condition of clostridia, but
57 its frequency increases markedly when a temperature abuse occurs and if the environmental
58 conditions are favourable for the growth of clostridia, i.e. water activity (a_w) higher than 0.93
59 and relatively high pH (Donnelly & Busta, 1981). These organisms may grow even if lactic acid
60 microbiota is present, such is the case of the Gouda and Emmental cheese varieties.

61 Irradiation has been used for the microbial disinfection of various food products in the US
62 (FSIS-USDA, 1999) and over 40 countries world-wide have approved about 100 irradiated food
63 products for consumption (Mahapatra, Muthukumarappan & Julson, 2005). Irradiation of dairy
64 products has not been studied as extensively as other food categories (Mahapatra et al., 2005).

65 Milk and several dairy products (such as yogurt, ice cream, mozzarella, cheddar and Feta
66 cheese) have been irradiated and different antimicrobial effectiveness, biochemical alterations
67 and sensorial changes have been observed (Abd El Baky, Farahat, Rabie & Mobasher, 1986;
68 Barba, Calvo, Herraiz & Santa-María, 2009; Hashisaka, Einstein, Rasco, Hungate & Dong,

69 1990; Hashisaka, Weagant & Dong, 1989; Konteles, Sinanoglou, Batrinou & Sflomos, 2009;
70 Seisa et al., 2004; Tsiotsias et al., 2002). In general, this type of treatment is compatible, from
71 the technological point of view, to the manufacturing process of cheese since it could be applied
72 just prior to its release into the market. However, the tolerance of cheese to irradiation must be
73 studied to optimize this treatment. In this regard, a more positive outcome for food tolerance to
74 irradiation has emerged once the interest was shifted from sterilization and other high-dose
75 irradiations to low-dose applications for sanitizing. For example, Cheddar cheese has been
76 experimentally subjected to low-dose irradiation for mold control/shelf life extension (Blank,
77 Shamsuzzaman & Sohal, 1992; Bongirwar & Kumta, 1967; Yüceer & Gündüz 1980),
78 Camembert cheese has been experimentally treated for lowering microbial counts to meet US
79 bacteriological standards (Boisseau, 1994) and to eradicate pathogens (Bougle & Stahl, 1993),
80 and undefined commercial cheese has been treated to enhance safety (Lalaguna, 2003) and to
81 study the changes in nutritive value associated with the treatment of radiation (Kung, Gaden &
82 King, 1953). These studies reported that doses below or equal to 3 kGy permitted the
83 technological objective sought.

84 This paper is an attempt to eliminate the clostridia responsible for the late blowing of cheese
85 until statistically negligible levels by applying E-beam irradiation. The effect of the irradiation
86 treatment on the sensory properties has also been evaluated since previous literature reported
87 (Blank & Cumming, 2001) that the irradiation treatment of dairy products generates
88 unacceptable off odours and flavours because of the formation of radiolytic products especially
89 in high lipid-based foods.

90

91 **2. Materials and Methods**

92

93 *2.1. General characteristics of cheese used in the experiments*

94 Commercial cheese made from pasteurized cow's milk was used. The production was typical of
95 semi-cured cheese; it is made adding a lactic starter culture and with a relatively enzymatic
96 coagulation (clotting temperature approximately 36 °C for 45 min) which gives rise to an elastic

97 and impermeable curd. Cheeses were ripened at 12 -14 °C under a relative humidity of 88%
98 before commercialization. The product is marketable in both prismatic blocks (30 cm in length)
99 of square base (12 x 12 cm) and slices (2 mm thick) with a ripening time of about three months.
100 If at this time the late blowing was not present, the level of *C. tyrobutyricum* spores (and related
101 species) was considered to be negligible. Therefore, this cheese could be used for the
102 inoculation experiments.

103

104 2.2. Organism

105 One strain of *Clostridium tyrobutyricum* ATCC 25755 was used. Spores were maintained by
106 freezing (- 40 °C) in a RCM (Reinforced Clostridial Medium. CM0149, Oxoid) agar free and
107 with 5% glycerol added. Fresh cultures were prepared by transferring 1 mL of thawed sample
108 into RCM agar free in an anaerobic jar and cultured at 37 °C for 72 hours. The culture was then
109 centrifuged (at 4 °C) and the pellet suspended into a beaker with 50 mL of 0.85% NaCl (w/v)
110 sterile saline solution, which yielded a bacterial load of approximately 10^8 cells mL⁻¹. Slices
111 were contaminated by immersion in the beaker for about 10 seconds. A large number of cells
112 were used to precisely determine the kill kinetic.

113

114 2.3. Sample preparation and irradiation treatment

115 Whole cheeses (3.5 kg weight unit) packed individually into impermeable plastic bags were
116 purchased in a local supermarket. Slices of about 10 grams (2 mm thickness) were cut in an
117 electric machine, whose knife and contact surfaces were previously deeply cleaned and finally
118 washed with sterile distilled water. To study the effect of E-beam irradiation on the survival of
119 *Clostridium tyrobutyricum*, slices were contaminated as described above. Both, uncontaminated
120 and contaminated slices were then vacuum-packaged to reach about 20 kPa in 20 x 20 cm
121 laminated film bags of low gas permeability (diffusion coefficient of 35 cm³/24h m² bar to
122 oxygen and 150 cm³/24h m² bar to carbon dioxide). Once the samples were vacuum-packaged,
123 they were transferred into insulated polystyrene boxes to the irradiation plant (Ionisos Iberica,
124 S.A., Tarancón, Cuenca, Spain) and irradiated under an electron beam radiation source, which

125 operates at 10 MeV. Experiments were made in triplicate and performed at room temperature
126 (18 - 20°C). The radiation doses employed were between 1 and 8 kGy for microbial analyses
127 and 1, 2 and 3 kGy for physico-chemical, texture, colour and sensory determinations, which
128 were applied to slices packed either individually for microbiological studies or in 3 - 6 units of
129 slices of the above mentioned size or in cylinder blocks (1.5 cm height and 2 cm base diameter)
130 for physic-chemical and sensory analyses. The actual dose absorbed by samples was checked by
131 determining the absorbance of cellulose triacetate dosimeters (ASTM, 2000) simultaneously
132 irradiated with samples. The temperature increase during treatment was less than 2 °C. After
133 irradiation treatment, samples were transferred to the laboratory and stored both at 4 °C and at
134 the ripening temperature (14 °C) until use. Three irradiation treatments were carried out, at three
135 different times, following the procedure described above.

136

137 *2.4. Microbial analyses*

138 To count the survivors, first, the slices were weighed, then, they were homogenized with 20 mL
139 of 0.85% NaCl (w/v) sterile saline solution in a sterile Stomacher bag. Total viable counts
140 (TVC) were determined by the pour-plate method using Plate Count Agar (PCA, Difco) as
141 culture medium. *C. tyrobutyricum* spores were numbered from the above homogenate after
142 heating the sample at 80 °C for 10 minutes. To count clostridia, the culture used was RCM
143 added to 1.8% of Bacteriological agar No 1 (LP0011, Oxoid) and the incubation was performed
144 in anaerobiosis jars, using AnaeroGen (AN0035, Oxoid) as the agent for the generation of
145 anaerobic conditions. The anaerobic atmosphere was controlled with the anaerobic indicator
146 BR0055B (Oxoid). Plates were incubated for 48 h at 37 °C and 32 °C for clostridium and TVC,
147 respectively. Colonies were enumerated with a Digital S Colony counter (J.P. Selecta,
148 Barcelona, Spain).

149 The growth curves were constructed according to the Baranyi model (Baranyi & Roberts, 1994)
150 regardless the count down observed in the first days of storage.

151

152 *2.5. Physico-chemical analysis*

153 The pH was determined in a homogenate of the sample with distilled water (1:10) (w/v), using a
154 Crison Digit-501 pH meter (Crison Instruments LTD, Barcelona, Spain). Water activity (a_w)
155 was measured using a Decagon CX1 hygrometer (Decagon Devices Inc., Pullman, WA, USA)
156 at 25°C. Moisture content (oven air-drying method) and ash (muffle furnace) were analyzed
157 following AOAC (1995). The protein (Kjeldhal nitrogen) and fat content of the cheese were
158 determined using the methods of the AOAC (1995) and Bligh and Dyer, described by Hanson &
159 Olley (1963), respectively.

160

161 *2.6. Texture profile analysis and colour measurements*

162 The texture profile analysis (TPA) was performed to assay the texture (Bourne, 1978;
163 Szczesniak, 1986). This analysis was carried out at about 22 °C, using a TA.XT2i SMS Stable
164 Micro Systems Texture Analyser (Stable Microsystems Ltd., Surrey, England) with the Texture
165 Expert programmes. For analysis, a cylindrical probe P/25 was used. This procedure involved
166 the preparation of four cheese cylinders of 1.5 cm in height and 2 cm in diameter from each
167 sample. A double compression cycle test was performed with up to 50% compression of the
168 original portion height with an aluminium cylinder probe of 2 cm in diameter. A time of 5 sec
169 was allowed to elapse between the two compression cycles. The following parameters were
170 quantified (Herrero et al., 2007): hardness, springiness, adhesiveness and cohesiveness.

171 Colour measurements were performed using a tristimulus colorimeter (Minolta Chroma Meter
172 CR300, Minolta Corporation, NJ) at three different analysis times (0, 8 and 21 days after
173 irradiation and storage at 4 °C). The L^* (lightness), a^* (redness) and b^* (yellowness)
174 parameters were measured ten times on the surface of the cheese slices at periods of 0, 4, 24 and
175 48 hours after opening the vacuum-pack. After the first colour measurement (just after opening
176 the bags), samples were kept at room temperature without protection, i.e. exposed to the
177 ambient air. Environmental conditions were 20–24 °C and about 43% relative humidity.

178

179 *2.7. Sensory analysis*

180 To determine the possible sensory differences among the non-treated (0 kGy) and irradiated

181 samples (1, 2 and 3 kGy), a triangular, a rank order and a descriptive test were performed.

182 Samples were evaluated by a panel of twenty tasters (ten females and ten males) selected from
183 the members of the Department of Nutrition, Food Science and Technology of the Complutense
184 University of Madrid. The panellists were previously trained in the sensory assessment of dairy
185 products. During the training, reference models (rotten egg, bloody, fishy, barbecued corn,
186 burnt, sulfur, metallic, wet dog, alcohol or acetic acid, hot culture medium, scalded feather,
187 pungent pepper, spoiled milk) were prepared in order to familiarize the testers with the expected
188 flavours yielded from E-beam treatment. To reduce fatigue, panel members conducted three
189 sessions per day with a minimum break of 1 hour between sessions. The evaluation was carried
190 out between meals, after breakfast and before the midday meal.

191 Before opening the vacuum-bag, the samples were left out to temperate for 20 minutes at room
192 temperature. The evaluations were performed in individual booths built according to the
193 International Standards Organization DP 66.58 criteria (ISO, 1981a). The tasters received
194 unsalted crackers and room temperature water to clean the palate between samples. Three
195 independent tests were performed to evaluate appearance, odour, and flavour. White fluorescent
196 light was used during appearance analysis. Odour and flavour of samples were evaluated under
197 red light conditions just after opening the bags.

198 The triangle test (ISO, 1981b) was performed by the forced-choice option, in which the tasters
199 must choose the sample that, in their opinion, is different. All the possible combinations of
200 untreated and irradiated samples were tested. These sensory analyses were carried out during the
201 0 and the 1st day after treatment, the 12th and 13th, 26th and 27th day of storage at 4 °C. To
202 complement the triangle test, judges were asked to indicate their reasons for selecting one
203 particular sample of the three used in the analysis.

204 At the rank order test, the judges were instructed to rank samples in order of preference,
205 according to the proximity of the sensory characteristic (appearance, odour and flavour) of the
206 sample analyzed to the optimal sensory quality of the cheese slices. For this, a four point scale
207 (in which 1 corresponded to the lowest preference and 4 to the highest preference) was used. No
208 repetitions were allowed. Results of the rank order test were used to obtain the sum of ranks,

209 which corresponds to the sum of scores of cheese preference for a specific sensory characteristic
210 [calculating the sum of the products of values given to each sample on a four point scale (from 1
211 to 4) by the number of times that each sample was allocated to a specific score]. The rank order
212 test was performed on 2nd, 14th and 28th days after samples treatment and storage at 4 °C.
213 Panellists were also asked to give information about the cheese slice characteristics (appearance,
214 odour and flavour and any off-sensory aspect) following a profile descriptive analysis as well as
215 about the acceptance for consumption (acceptable without modifications, acceptable with minor
216 modifications and rejected or not adequate for consumption). This procedure was carried out on
217 the 3rd, 15th and 29th day after irradiation treatment and storage at 4 °C.

218

219 *2.8. Statistical analysis*

220 The coefficient of determination (R^2) of curves and the 95% confidence limits (CL) of D-values
221 were calculated by Excel (Microsoft, Redmond, Wash). For physical and chemical data
222 analysis, a one-way analysis of variance and a Duncan's procedure to multiple mean
223 comparisons were carried out using a Statgraphics Plus version 5.0 for Windows (Statistical
224 Graphics Corporation, Rockville, Md., U.S.A.). In order to describe the effects of the irradiation
225 treatment and storage time on colour parameters and sensory results, the response surface
226 methodology was used.

227 The results of the triangular test were analyzed according to the tables of the minimum number
228 of panellists with correct answers in order to establish the significant level (Pedredo &
229 Pangborn, 1989).

230 The significant level of data obtained in the rank order test was determined by Friedman's rank
231 addition according to the model proposed by Joanes (1985) and the tables for multiple
232 comparison procedures for analysis of ranked data (Christensen, Ogden, Dunn & Eggett, 2006).

233

234 **3. Results and Discussion**

235

236 *3.1. Microbiological analyses*

237 The survival curve of *C. tyrobutyricum* is shown in Figure 1. The count of non-irradiated
238 samples was lower than that which was determined at 1 kGy. This phenomenon is very common
239 in heat treatment experiments (Stumbo, 1973), which has been explained to be caused as a result
240 of an activation of spores during heating where the number of spores activated exceeds those
241 that are killed. In the present case, the same situation could occur. Therefore, the regression
242 equation was calculated avoiding the point of non-irradiated samples on the abscise axis (Figure
243 1). As expected, the rate of clostridia death by radiation was fitted to a first-order inactivation
244 reaction, according to the equation (1):

$$245 \quad y = - 0.5645x + 7.3171 \quad (R^2 = 0.98) \quad (1)$$

246 where,

247 y is the logarithm of colony forming units (c.f.u.) g^{-1}

248 and

249 x is the irradiation dose (kGy).

250

251 From this equation, a decimal reduction value (D value) of 1.77 kGy was determined, which
252 predicts that, for example, a 3 kGy treatment will cause a 96% reduction of spores originally
253 present, i.e., it will decrease nearly a hundred-fold the possibility spoilage.

254 Anaerobic spores, particularly those of *C. tyrobutyricum* are present in soil, bovine faeces and
255 silage (Donnelly & Busta, 1981; Read, Bradshaw & Francis, 1970; Vries & Stadhouders, 1977);
256 it is from these sources that spores reach the raw milk. The common raw milk spore content is
257 variable depending on the sanitation measures, which are very adequate to control spore
258 contamination since the major source is, together with the silage, the faecal one (Su & Ingham,
259 2000). In France, payment of milk depending on spore counts was formerly proposed (Henry,
260 1977), stating a load of 780 spores L^{-1} as a satisfactory level for anaerobic spores in raw milk.
261 Donnelly & Busta (1981) inferred that milk could contain no more than 1 anaerobic spore mL^{-1} .
262 Later, in a survey performed in 1997 (Ingham, Hassler, Tsai & Ingham, 1998), fourteen samples
263 of pasteurized milk from eight Gouda cheese plants were analyzed. A concentration of
264 endospores of lactate-fermenting, gas-producing *Clostridium* spp. from 5.0×10^{-2} to 1.7×10^0

265 spores mL⁻¹, with an average load of 0.36 spores mL⁻¹ was found; this is similar in nature to the
266 data reported by Coulon, Varignier & Darne (1991) in France and Vissers, Driehuis, Te Giffer,
267 De Jong & Lankvel (2007) following a year-long survey of 24 dairy farms and one half of those
268 reported by Henry (1977). Klijn, Nieuwenhor, Hoolwerf, Van der Waals & Weerkamp (1995)
269 recommended that milk used for manufacturing Gouda cheese should contain less than one *C.*
270 *tyrobutyricum* spore per 10 mL. Assuming that both 10 litres (with an agreement of a
271 contamination of 3600 spores as indicated by Ingham et al., 1998) of milk yield a fresh cheese
272 of 1 Kg and that the total number of spores present in milk is retained in the curd, the cheese
273 would contain 3.6 spores g⁻¹. This would result in late blowing since it has been reported that 1
274 spore g⁻¹ is enough to produce the defect (0.1 spore mL⁻¹ of milk according to Klijn et al, 1995).
275 On the other hand, from the experiments carried out by Klijn et al. (1995) and Ingham et al.
276 (1998), there is an estimated doubling time for *C. tyrobutyricum* of about 5 - 7 days at 13 °C.
277 Assuming that spoilage occurs when the *C. tyrobutiycum* load is at the level of 10⁷ c.f.u. g⁻¹ of
278 cheese, the defect would appear after about 21.4 generations, i.e., after about 129 days.
279 However, the application of E-beam reduces the spore load by two log units. Thus, the original
280 bacterial concentration would be 0.036 spores g⁻¹ and, in this case, 28 generations would be
281 required to reach the critical load. Accordingly, it would produce an important shelf-life
282 extension (about 168 days). In addition, it is likely that the surviving bacteria have to repair the
283 damage caused by treatment with E-beam, thus leading to an extension of the either a lag phase
284 or a doubling time, as has been observed in *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Listeria monocytogenes*
285 (Cabeza, Cambero, Núñez, Medina, de la Hoz & Ordóñez., 2010) which, in turn, would cause a
286 further extension of the shelf-life. Therefore, the results obtained in the present study indicate
287 that the E-beam treatment (at a low dose) could be considered an alternative strategy to reduce,
288 or at least prolong the initiation moment of late blowing cheese and thus increase its shelf-life.
289 This treatment could be included as a hurdle in the design of an effective combined process
290 together with current methods (such as lysozyme addition and bacto-fugation) to prevent the
291 growth of *C. tyrobutyricum* spores.

292 In the dairy industry, several general measures may be applied to control the growth of
293 anaerobic spores, (Donnelly & Busta, 1981; Ingham et al., 1998): avoiding the contamination of
294 raw milk, which may be controlled with sanitation measures (Donnelly & Busta, 1981), feeding
295 cows with silage with very low spore content (Vissers et al., 2007), storing in refrigeration
296 conditions, keeping low pH (< 4.6), reducing a_w (< 0.93), adding preservative (e.g. lysozyme,
297 nisine and nitrites), inactivation (usually heat), and removing spores (e.g. bactofugation). Most
298 of these control measures are not easily applicable in the cheese industry. The removal of
299 bacterial cells and spores from raw milk by bactofugation at approximately 9,000xg force is
300 actually used as one means of reducing the number of anaerobic spores in milk. This method
301 may remove a 75 – 99% of spores (Waes & Van Heddeghem, 1990). However, the resulting
302 pellet can be added back to the cheese milk after thermal processing, thus avoiding the yield
303 losses otherwise associated with bactofugation (Kosikowski & Mistry, 1997). Another method
304 used to avoid the late blowing defect is to prevent the germination of clostridia spores during
305 ripening. Salt concentration and ripening temperature are known to influence the late blowing
306 defect in Gouda cheese caused by the growth of *C. tyrobutyricum* strains. Kleter, Lammers &
307 Vos, (1984) reported that an initial salt in moisture content of 2.9% and a final salt in moisture
308 content of 4.0% prevented late blowing in Gouda cheese ripened at 18 °C. However, this
309 approach can hardly be used because of the current tendency to reduce the sodium content of
310 processed foods. Refrigeration is perhaps, the best solution to avoid the growth of anaerobic
311 spore-forming bacteria. This technology is consistently applied for storage of ready-to-eat
312 (RTE) processed cheese (e.g. slices, dices) achieving, indeed, a very long shelf-life. It has been
313 reported that *C. tyrobutyricum* germinate at 13 °C in Gouda cheese slurry (Su & Ingham, 2000).
314 Therefore, this approach can not be employed for semi-hard and hard cheese since they have to
315 be ripened during a long time (more than 2 - 3 months) at a higher temperature (usually 13 – 15
316 °C) to attain the characterized sensory quality of each cheese variety. During this time, the
317 anaerobic spores are slowly growing, which may lead to the late blowing spoilage afterwards.
318 To control the growth of the clostridia responsible for the late blowing of cheese by E-beam
319 irradiation, the raw milk or the cheese has to be treated at different times of ripening. Therefore,

320 to explore the effect of the irradiation treatment in the ripening process, the behaviour of the
321 natural microbiota of the cheese after the irradiation was studied (Figure 2). Since the non-
322 sporeforming microbiota present in the cheese, mainly lactic acid bacteria (LAB), is much more
323 radiosensitive than the spores, a 3 kGy treatment also produced a very important kill of these
324 organisms, in such a way that in the present experiment the mesophilic aerobic counts were
325 reduced from 7.68 log c.f.u. g⁻¹ in non-treated samples to 6.30 log c.f.u. g⁻¹, 4.72 log c.f.u. g⁻¹ and
326 3.14 log c.f.u. g⁻¹ after the application of 1, 2 and 3 kGy, respectively (Figure 2).

327 From these data, a D-value of about 0.66 kGy may be estimated. This value is somewhat higher
328 for other non-spore-forming bacteria and borders on the levels of *S. aureus* (Grant & Patterson,
329 1992; Thayer & Boyd, 1992) and *L. monocytogenes* (Cabeza, Cambero, de la Hoz & Ordoñez,
330 2007; Mendonca, Romero, Lihono, Nannapaneni & Jonson, 2004.), which are considered,
331 among the pathogens, to be the most radio-resistant organisms. However, these results are close
332 to those reported by other authors for LAB in meat, since a treatment of 2.5 kGy produced only
333 a 3.4 log reduction while more than five reductions were observed for other bacteria such as
334 pseudomonads, Enterobacteriaceae or *Brochothrix thermosphacta* (Niemand, Van der Linde &
335 Holzappel, 1983). Additionally, it must be taken into account that cheese always presents a
336 mixed microbiota and the radioresistance of bacteria may be variable.

337 In the early days of storage at 14 °C (about a month in samples maintained at 4 °C), a further
338 decline was observed in the number of bacteria to be recovered afterwards (Figure 3, dotted
339 lines). This phenomenon had already been previously noticed in experiments with *S. aureus* and
340 *L. monocytogenes* (Cabeza et al., 2010). These authors explained the situation was due to the
341 DNA damage caused by the radiation, the resuscitation being dependent on the ability of
342 bacteria to repair the DNA damages. After this phase, the growth of microbiota may be
343 considered to be normal although it happens at a lower rate. Furthermore, at both storage
344 temperatures, the greater the dose, the higher the generation times (*g* value), which is in
345 agreement with previous literature (Cabeza et al., 2010). From curves of Figure 3, *g* values of
346 66, 92 and 102 hours may be calculated at 4 °C when 1, 2 and 3 kGy were respectively applied.
347 The same parameters after storage at 14 °C were 18, 22, and 25 hours. The differences in the *g*

348 values between 4 and 14 °C conditioned the time that lactic microbiota took to reach the normal
349 levels (around 10^7 c.f.u g^{-1}). So, it was necessary 10 and 12 days at 14 °C when the doses
350 applied were 1 kGy and 2 kGy, respectively, but at 4°C, the microbiota needed 40 and 50 days,
351 respectively. When treatment was 3 kGy microbiota grew much more slowly thus after 100 days
352 at 4 °C, the 10^7 c.f.u g^{-1} level was not yet attained. Obviously, this is due to a more severe
353 damage of bacteria, which is not able to be repaired.

354

355 *3.2. General physico-chemical characteristics, texture and colour evaluation*

356 Physico-chemical parameters (moisture, protein, fat, ash, a_w and pH) of cheese samples, both
357 non-irradiated and irradiated (1, 2 and 3 kGy), were measured immediately following irradiation
358 and also three weeks later (storage at 4 °C). No statistically significant difference ($P > 0.05$) was
359 observed among the irradiated and non-irradiated samples, for all the parameters measured. The
360 chemical composition (% on wet matter) of cheese was: moisture 44.68 ± 0.54 , protein
361 27.89 ± 0.38 , fat 23.24 ± 3.02 and ash 1.83 ± 0.01 . The a_w and pH were, respectively, 0.958 ± 0.005
362 and 5.86 ± 0.13 . Several authors (Konteles et al., 2009; Tsiotsias et al., 2002) reported similar
363 findings for different types of cheese exposed to irradiation at low doses. The preservation of
364 the typical physico-chemical characteristics of the irradiated cheese is considered favourable,
365 since these are closely related to the sensory profile of cheese (Konteles et al., 2009).

366 In the TPA analysis, irradiated and untreated samples showed similar values for adhesiveness
367 (about -0.96 ± 0.35 N x s) and springiness (around 0.006 ± 0.0005 cm). However, a significant (P
368 < 0.05) decrease of hardness was observed ranging from 40.42 ± 4.42 to 23.40 ± 5.15 N for
369 samples treated at 0 and 3 kGy. This was associated with an increase of the cohesiveness
370 (around 0.68 ± 0.03 and 0.73 ± 0.02 for samples irradiated at 0 and 3 kGy, respectively) at doses \geq
371 2 kGy (Figure 4). The texture differences between irradiated and untreated samples were
372 maintained at different storage times with a similar intensity. These results could be due to the
373 effect of irradiation on the ultrastructure of cheese. A feasible explanation can be the possibility
374 of the aggregation of protein causing changes of the milk gel rheological behaviour. A similar
375 effect has been reported in several irradiated foods, a case in point is soybean protein (El-

376 Moneim, Afify & Shousha, 1988). It is also possible that irradiation cause disruption of protein
377 and distortion in the ultrastructure gel of cheese. Radiolysis of proteins mainly induces a
378 fragmentation and/or aggregation of the protein and an inactivation of the enzyme, according to
379 Audette-Stuart, Houee-Levin & Potier (2005). Other authors (Konteles et al., 2009) have
380 reported no effect on the texture of feta cheese type due to irradiation probably because these
381 cheeses have a firmer texture, as well as a different structure and chemical composition.
382 The L^* , a^* and b^* values of cheese slices were determined on the product surface a few minutes
383 (considered as 0 h), 4, 24 and 48 hours after opening the vacuum-package and consequently
384 exposure to air. A clear influence ($P < 0.05$) of the irradiation dose (0, 1, 2 and 3 kGy) was
385 observed for the a^* and b^* values. The irradiation treatment produced a significant ($P < 0.05$)
386 increase of the a^* value, following the order: -2.17 ± 0.21 , -1.96 ± 0.06 , -1.90 ± 0.10 and -1.64 ± 0.06
387 for 0, 1, 2 and 3 kGy, respectively at 0 days after irradiation treatment and just after opening the
388 vacuum-package. In addition, a significant ($P < 0.05$) effect of the storage time at 4 °C was also
389 observed in all samples (irradiated and untreated), consisting of a decrease in a^* values. This
390 effect increased the differences between untreated and irradiated samples at 21 days of storage
391 at 4 °C (just after opening vacuum-package, the a^* values varied between -3.23 ± 0.32 for 0 kGy
392 and -2.01 ± 0.10 for irradiated samples at 3 kGy). For a better understanding of these relations,
393 the estimated response surface for the a^* value (just after opening vacuum-package) using the
394 dose (kGy) of irradiation treatment and the storage time (day) at 4 °C is shown in Figure 5. The
395 regression equation ($P < 0.0001$) obtained was (2):

396

$$397 \quad a^* = -2.24 + 0.23(\text{dose}) - 0.11(\text{storage time}) - 0.03(\text{dose})^2 + 0.003(\text{storage time})^2 + 0.016$$

398 (dose)(storage time). (2)

399

400 In general, it is possible to assume that, at the same storage time, the higher the irradiation dose
401 the greater the a^* value. This behaviour was intensified when the samples were exposed to air
402 because the a^* value of the irradiated samples above 1 kGy decreased ($P < 0.05$) with the
403 increase in time since the opening of the vacuum-package (for example, the a^* values for the

404 irradiated samples at 3 kGy varied from -1.6 to -2.1 just after opening the vacuum-package and
405 from -3.2 to -3.0 after 48 hours of exposure to air).

406 The irradiation treatment also produced a significant ($P < 0.05$) decrease of the b^* -value, which
407 varied (just after opening vacuum-package) from a maximum of 18.70 ± 0.33 in untreated
408 samples to a minimum of about 14.58 ± 0.36 for samples irradiated at 3 kGy. Figure 5 shows that
409 b^* value was affected by the doses of irradiation treatment and the time of storage at 4 °C. The
410 regression equation was (3):

411

$$412 \quad b^* = 18.68 - 2.12(\text{dose}) - 0.08(\text{storage time}) + 0.25(\text{dose})^2 + 0.004(\text{storage time})^2 - \\ 413 \quad 0.009(\text{dose})(\text{storage time}). \quad (3)$$

414

415 As can be observed in Figure 5, the effect of irradiation treatment in the b^* value parameter was
416 maintained at different storage times with a similar intensity. This colour parameter remained
417 statistically unchanged ($P > 0.05$) after opening the vacuum-package and the consequent
418 exposure to air of the sample (from 0 to 48 hours).

419 These results may be correlated with the colour changes observed by other authors (Seisa et al.,
420 2004; Tsiotsias et al., 2002) in different types of cheese after irradiation. Similarly, the
421 irradiation (particularly at 4.7 kGy) increased redness (a^* value) and decreased yellowness (b^*
422 value) of Feta (Konteles et al., 2009) and Cheddar (Seisa et al., 2004).

423 No effects ($P > 0.05$) of irradiation dose and storage time were observed in the L^* parameter of
424 the product just after opening the package; average values were of 83.5 ± 1.45 just after opening
425 vacuum-package. The L^* value decreased ($P < 0.05$) after exposure to air of the irradiated and
426 untreated samples, with minimum values of around 80.0 at 48 hours after opening the vacuum-
427 package. This decrease may probably be due to surface water loss associated with exposure to
428 air.

429 Different results have been reported for irradiated cheese for lightness (L^* value). A decrease of
430 this colour parameter has been described in irradiated Feta cheese (Konteles et al., 2009) while

431 irradiated “Anthotyros” was described as brighter (Tsiotsias et al., 2002). These differences are
432 probably related to fat and moisture contents and characteristic structure of every cheese variety.
433

434 3.3. Sensory analysis

435 As a general statement, it is important to advance that samples subjected to E-beam maintained
436 their global sensory quality, which means that they were adequate for consumption, even those
437 treated with a dose of 3 kGy. Nevertheless, when treated (at 1, 2 and 3 kGy) and non-irradiated
438 samples (control) were compared, some changes were observed (Table 1). Significant
439 differences ($P < 0.05$) for appearance between control (non-irradiated) and irradiated samples
440 were found in the triangular analysis carried out after treatment (0 - 1st day) and during the
441 second (12- 13th days) and third week (26- 27th days) of storage at 4 °C (Table 1). In the visual
442 aspect, the descriptive analysis detected slight colour changes. The samples treated with 2 and 3
443 kGy were judged to be lighter, less yellow and white-gray. These sensory results are in
444 agreement with those obtained by the instrumental colour analysis mentioned above, since a
445 progressive decrease of yellowness (b^* -values) was observed as the intensity of the irradiation
446 treatment increased. This could be related with the decrease of carotenoid pigments by the
447 radiation effect, which corresponds to the bleaching of irradiated samples, possibly as a result of
448 the bleaching of its pigments. Similar finding have been reported for different irradiated foods
449 (Herrero, Ordóñez, Carmona, de la Hoz & Cambero, 2009; Konteles et al., 2009). There is
450 evidence (Bosset & Flückiger, 1989) that yogurts exposed to light were redder and less yellow
451 than yogurts stored in darkness and this was correlated with the degradation of riboflavin and β -
452 carotene. An increase in redness and a decrease in yellowness have also been reported for light
453 oxidized cheeses and other dairy products (Juric, Bertelsen, Mortensen & Petersen, 2003;
454 Kristensen, Orlie, Mortensen, Brockhoff & Skibsted, 2000; Mortensen, Bertelsen, Mortensen
455 & Stapelfeldt, 2004).

456 The slight appearance changes did not affect ($P > 0.05$) the order of preference of the samples,
457 and similar results for untreated and irradiated cheese were obtained in the rank order test
458 (Figure 6). This was probably because the commercial cheese made from pasteurized cow's

459 milk presents a wide variety of colours. Some panellists considered the cheese that was lighter
460 in appearance to be better or have a sharper taste.

461 In the odour triangular analysis, significant differences ($P < 0.05$) were found after two weeks
462 of storage at 4 °C between the samples radiated at doses ≥ 2 kGy and the untreated ones (Table
463 1). However, a significant ($P < 0.05$) decrease in the odour preference of the samples was only
464 observed for a dose of 3 kGy after three weeks of storage at 4 °C (Figure 6). In irradiated
465 samples, the panellists described less odour intensity to milk and cream and off-odours defined
466 as rancid and burnt (very slight at 2 and weak at 3 kGy). These results may be related to the
467 changes in the volatile profile of radiated milk fat. Several authors (Khatri, Libbey & Day,
468 1966; Merritt, Forss, Angelini & Bazinet, 1967) have reported that irradiation can induce the
469 formation of n-alkanes, oxidized butteroil, saturated hydrocarbons, fatty acids, and lactones.

470 For flavour, significant differences ($P < 0.05$) between non-irradiated and irradiated were found
471 only in the 3 kGy samples (Table 1) in the triangle analysis carried out after different storage
472 times at 4 °C. In the irradiated samples at dose ≥ 2 kGy negligible (at 2 kGy) and weak (at 3
473 kGy) off-flavours were detected. These off-flavours were defined as bitter, pungent, metallic,
474 rancid and burned. The off-flavours were minimised during storage. A significant ($P < 0.05$)
475 lower preference for flavour evaluation was only observed at 3 kGy during the first and second
476 week of storage at 4 °C (Figure 6), which shows that once the threshold of 2 kGy is exceeded,
477 the irradiation negatively affects the flavour acceptance or preference. However, after three
478 weeks, lower differences were observed between irradiated and non-treated samples (Figure 6),
479 probably due to the decrease of the off-flavor intensity. These samples, however, were always
480 described as adequate for consumption considering the off-flavor as a minor sensory change.

481 These results are in agreement with those obtained by several authors for different types of
482 cheese. Off-flavour development and colour changes have also been detected at greater dose
483 than 1.5 kGy when applied to Turkish Kashar cheese (Yüceer & Gündüz, 1980). Similar
484 findings have been reported for Cheddar (Bongirwar & Kumta, 1967) and Mozzarella cheese
485 (Hashisaka et al., 1990). However, no taste differences were found between irradiated (3.2 kGy)
486 and non-irradiated Gouda (Rosenthal, Martinot, Lindner, Juven & Ben-Hur, 1983). Feta cheese

487 presented off-flavour when was exposed to 4.7 kGy (Konteles et al., 2009). The non-permanent
488 intensity in the off-flavour of the irradiated cheese (such as Feta, Anthotyros and Ras cheese)
489 has also been reported by several authors (Abd El Baky et al., 1986, Konteles et al., 2009;
490 Tsiotsias et al. 2002) and its dissipation a few weeks later (Buttery, Guadagni & Ling, 1973;
491 Kochhar, 1996; Lee & Ahn, 2003; Nawar, 1985). These authors suggested that during the first
492 days after irradiation, the secondary oxidation products are volatile and off-flavour is sensory
493 detectable. In the weeks that follow, the oxidation phenomena, even at 4 °C, continue and
494 possibly the polymerized or isomerized secondary oxidation products become less volatile or
495 have a lower sensorial threshold, consequently, the cheese off-flavour is dissipated.

496

497 **4. Conclusions**

498 In summary, an alternative strategy is proposed for reducing the anaerobic spore load of cheese
499 to diminish the late blowing of cheese. The E-beam irradiation at a dose of 3 kGy gave rise to a
500 96% reduction of the *C. tyrobutyricum* spores. This irradiation dose produced a weak off-odour
501 and off-flavour, although the samples were considered by testers to be acceptable for
502 consumption. A reduction in the spoilage of nearly 99% that does not adversely affecting the
503 sensory properties is considered to be a very favourable benefit from a commercial point of
504 view.

505

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507

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511

512 **References**

513 Abd El Baky, A. A., Farahat, S. M., Rabie, A. M., & Mobasher, S. A. (1986). The manufacture
514 of Ras cheese from gamma irradiated milk. *Food Chemistry*, 20, 201–212.

515 AOAC. (1995). *Official methods of analysis* (16th ed.). Washington DC. Association of Official
516 Analytical Chemists.

517 ASTM (American Society for Testing and Materials). (2000). E1650-97e1 Standard practice for
518 use of cellulose acetate dosimetry systems. Vol. 12.02.

519 Audette-Stuart, M., Houee-Levin, C., & Potier, M. (2005). Radiation-induced protein
520 fragmentation and inactivation in liquid and solid aqueous solutions. Role of OH and
521 electrons. *Radiation Physics and Chemistry*, 72, 301–306.

522 Baranyi, J., & Roberts, T. A. (1994). A dynamic approach to predicting bacterial growth in
523 food. *International Journal of Food Microbiology*, 23, 277-294.

524 Barba, C., Calvo, M. M., Herraiz, M., & Santa-María, G. (2009). Detection of radiolytic
525 hydrocarbons by supercritical fluid extraction and gas chromatographic-mass
526 spectrometric analysis of irradiated cheese. *Food Chemistry*, 114, 1517-1522.

527 Blank, G., & Cumming, R. (2001). Irradiation. In N. A. M. Eskin and D. S. Robinson (Eds.),
528 *Food Shelf Life Stability. Chemical, Biochemical and Microbiological Changes* (pp. 87-
529 128). Florida: CRC Press LLC.

530 Blank, G., Shamsuzzaman, K., & Sohal, S. (1992). Use of electron beam irradiation for mold
531 decontamination on Cheddar cheese. *Journal of Dairy Science*, 75, 13-18.

532 Bongirwar, D. R., & Kumta, U. S. (1967). Preservation of cheese with combined use of gamma-
533 rays and sorbic acid. *International Journal of Applied Radiation and Isotopes*, 18, 133-
534 134.

535 Boisseau, P. (1994). Irradiation and the food industry in France. *Food Technology*, 48, 138-140.

536 Bosset, J. O., & Flückiger, E. (1989). Packaging and maintenance of food quality: effect on
537 photosensitivity of different types of yogurt. *Lebensmittel–Wissenschaft and Technologie*,
538 22, 292–300.

539 Bogle, D., & Stahl, V. (1993). Eradication de bacteries pathogenes (*Listeria monocytogenes* et
540 *Salmonella*) de Camemberts au lait cru par rayonnements ionisants. *Cost-benefits aspects*
541 *of food irradiation processing*. Proceeding Series, (pp. 103-111). IAEA. Vienna.

542 Bourne, M. C. (1978). Texture profile analysis. *Food Technology*, 32, 62-72.

543 Buttery, R. C., Guadagni, D. G., & Ling, L. C. (1973). Flavor compounds: volatilities in
544 vegetable oil and oil water mixture. Estimation of odor thresholds. *Journal of Agricultural*
545 *and Food Chemistry*, 21, 198–201.

546 Cabeza, M. C., Cambero, M. I., de la Hoz, L., & Ordóñez, J. A. (2007). Optimization of E-beam
547 irradiation treatment to eliminate *Listeria monocytogenes* from ready-to-eat (RTE) cooked
548 ham. *Innovative Food Science & Emerging Technologies*, 8, 299-305.

549 Cabeza, M. C., Cambero, M. I., Núñez, M., Medina, M., de la Hoz, L., & Ordóñez, J. A. (2010).
550 Lack of growth of *Listeria monocytogenes* and *Staphylococcus aureus* in temperature
551 abuse of E-beam treated ready-to-eat (RTE) cooked ham. *Food Microbiology*, 27, 777-
552 782.

553 Christensen, Z. T., Ogden, L. V., Dunn, M. L., & Eggett, D. L. (2006). Multiple comparison
554 procedures for analysis of ranked data. *Journal of Food Science*, 71, 132–143.

555 Coulon, J. B., Varignier, M., & Darne, D. (1991) Contamination butyrique du lait de vache:
556 étude dans les exploitations de Haute-Loire. *Production Animale*, 4, 369-372.

557 Donnelly, L. S., & Busta, F. F. (1981). Anaerobic sporeforming microorganisms in dairy
558 products. *Journal of Dairy Science*, 64, 161-166.

559 El-Moneim, A., Afify, M. R., & Shousha, M. A. (1988). Effect of low-dose irradiation on
560 soybean protein solubility, trypsin inhibitor activity, and protein patterns separated by
561 polyacrylamide gel electrophoresis. *Journal of Agricultural Food Chemistry*, 36, 810–813.

562 FSIS-USDA. (1999). Irradiation of meat products. Federal Register Interim and Final Rules,
563 Docket No 99–0501F. Available at:
564 [http://www.fsis.usda.gov/regulations_&_policies/1999_Interim_&_Final_Rules_Index/in](http://www.fsis.usda.gov/regulations_&_policies/1999_Interim_&_Final_Rules_Index/index.asp)
565 [dex.asp](http://www.fsis.usda.gov/regulations_&_policies/1999_Interim_&_Final_Rules_Index/index.asp)

566 Grant, I. R., & Patterson, M. F. (1992). Sensitivity of foodborne pathogens to irradiation in the
567 components of a chilled ready meal. *Food Microbiology*, 9, 95–103.

568 Hanson, S. W. F., & Olley, J. (1963). Application of the Bligh and Dyer method of lipid
569 extraction to tissue homogenates. *Biochemical Journal*, 89, 101-102.

570 Hashisaka, A. E., Weagant, S. D., & Dong, F. M. (1989). Survival of *L. monocytogenes* in
571 mozzarella cheese and ice cream exposed to gamma irradiation. *Journal of Food*
572 *Protection*, 52, 490–492.

573 Hashisaka, A. E., Einstein, M. A., Rasco, B. A., Hungate, F. P., & Dong, F. M. (1990). Sensory
574 analysis of dairy products irradiated with cobalt-60 at -78 °C. *Journal of Food Science*, 55,
575 404-408.

576 Henry, A. (1977). Factors influencing contamination of milk by butiric acid bacteria spores.
577 *Revue Laitière Française*, 350, 81-83.

578 Herrero, A. M., Ordóñez, J. A., Romero de Avila, M. D., Herranz, B., Hoz, L., & Cambero, M.
579 I. (2007). Breaking strength of dry fermented sausages and their correlation with Texture
580 Profile Analysis (TPA) and physico-chemical characteristics. *Meat Science*, 77, 331-338.

581 Herrero, A. M., Ordóñez, J. A., Carmona, P., de la Hoz, L., & Cambero, M. I. (2009). Raman
582 spectroscopy studies of electron-beam irradiated cold-smoked salmon. *Food Research*
583 *International*, 42, 216-220.

584 Ingham, S. C., Hassler, J. R., Tsai, Y-W., & Ingham, B. H. (1998). Differentiation of lactate-
585 fermenting, gas-producing *Clostridium* spp. isolated from milk. *International Journal of*
586 *Food Microbiology*, 43, 173–183.

587 International Organization for Standardization. (1981a). Analyse sensorielle. Guide pour
588 l'implantation d'un local destiné aux analyses sensorielles. ISO/DP 66.58, Genève: ISO.

589 International Organization for Standardization. (1981b). Methodologie essai triangulaire. ISO
590 TC 34/SC 12, Genève: ISO.

591 Joanes, D. N. (1985). On a rank sum test due to Kramer. *Journal of Food Science*, 50, 1442–
592 1444.

593 Juric, M., Bertelsen, G., Mortensen, G., & Petersen, M. A. (2003). Light induced colour and
594 aroma changes in sliced modified atmosphere packaged semi-hard cheeses. *International*
595 *Dairy Journal*, 13, 239–249.

596 Khatri, L. L., Libbey, L. M., & Day, E. A. (1966). Gas chromatographic and mass spectral
597 identification of some volatile components of gamma-irradiated milk fat. *Journal of*
598 *Agricultural and Food Chemistry*, 14, 465-469.

599 Kleter, G., Lammers, W. L., & Vos, E. A. (1984). The influence of pH and concentration of
600 lactic acid and NaCl on the growth of *Clostridium tyrobutyricum* in whey and cheese. 2.
601 Experiments in cheese. *Netherlands Milk and Dairy Journal*, 38, 31-41.

602 Klijn, N., Nieuwenhof, F. F. J., Hoolwerf, J. D., Van Der Waals, C. B., & Weerkamp, A. H.
603 (1995). Identification of *Clostridium tyrobutyricum* as the causative agent of late blowing
604 in cheese by species-specific PCR amplification. *Applied and Environmental*
605 *Microbiology*, 61, 2919-2924.

606 Kochhar, S. P. (1996). Oxidation pathways to the formation of off-flavours. In Saxby, M. J.
607 (Ed.), *Food Taints and Off-flavours*, second edition (pp. 168-225), London: Blackie
608 Academic & Professional.

609 Konteles, S., Sinanoglou, V. J., Batrinou, A., & Sflomos, K. (2009). Effects of γ -irradiation on
610 *Listeria monocytogenes* population, colour, texture and sensory properties of Feta cheese
611 during cold storage. *Food Microbiology*, 26, 157-165.

612 Kosikowski, F. V., & Mistry, V. V. (1997). *Cheese and Fermented Milk Foods*. (3rd. Ed.).
613 Wesport, C. T.: F. V. Kosikowski, L. L. C.

614 Kristensen, D., Orlie, V., Mortensen, G., Brockhoff, P., & Skibsted, L. H. (2000). Light
615 induced oxidation in sliced Havarti cheese packaged in modified atmosphere.
616 *International Dairy Journal*, 10, 95-103.

617 Kung, H., Gaden, E., & King, C. (1953). Vitamins and enzymes in milk, effect of gamma-
618 radiation on activity. *Journal of Agricultural and Food Chemistry*, 1, 142-144.

619 Lalaguna, F. (2003). Physicochemical response of Palmita-type cheese to low-dose irradiation.
620 *Journal of Food Science*, 68, 26-30.

621 Lee, E. J., & Ahn, D. U. (2003). Production of volatiles from fatty acids and oils by irradiation.
622 *Journal of Food Science*, 68, 70-75.

623 Mahapatra, A. K., Muthukumarappan, K., & Julson, J. L. (2005). Applications of ozone,
624 bacteriocins and irradiation in food processing: a review. *Critical Reviews in Food Science*
625 *and Nutrition, 45*, 477–461.

626 Mendonca, A. F., Romero, M. G., Lihono, M. A., Nannapaneni, R., & Jonson, M. G. (2004).
627 Radiation resistance and virulence of *Listeria monocytogenes* Scott A following starvation
628 in physiological saline. *Journal of Food Protection, 67*, 470–474.

629 Merritt, C. Jr., Forss, D. A., Angelini, P., & Bazinet, M. L. (1967). Volatile compounds
630 produced by irradiation of butterfat. *Journal of the American Oil Chemists Society, 44*,
631 144-146.

632 Mortensen, G., Bertelsen, G., Mortensen, B., & Stapelfeldt, H. (2004). Light-induced changes in
633 packaged cheeses – a review. *International Dairy Journal, 14*, 85–102.

634 Nawar, W. W. (1985). Lipids. In O. R. Fennema (Ed.), *Food Chemistry, second ed., revised and*
635 *expanded* (pp. 139-244). New York. Marcel Dekker.

636 Niemand, J. G., Van der Linde, H. J., & Holzapfel, W. H. (1983) Shelf-life extension of minced
637 beef through combined treatment involving radiation. *Journal of Food Protection, 46*,
638 791-796.

639 Pedredo, F. D. L., & Pangborn, R. M. (1989). *Evaluación sensorial de los alimentos: métodos*
640 *analíticos*. México: Alhambra mexicana, (pp. 231-232), México.

641 Read, R. B. Jr., Bradshaw, J. G., & Francis, D. W. (1970). Growth and toxin production of
642 *Clostridium botulinum* type E in milk. *Journal of Dairy Science, 53*, 1183-1186.

643 Rosenthal, I., Martinot, M., Lindner, P., Juven, J., & Ben-Hur, E. (1983). A study of ionizing
644 radiation of dairy products. *Milchwissenschaft, 38*, 467-470.

645 Seisa, D., Osthoff, G., Hugo, C., Hugo, A., Bothma, C., & Van der Merwe, J. (2004). The effect
646 of low-dose gamma irradiation and temperature on the microbiological and chemical
647 changes during ripening of cheddar cheese. *Radiation Physics and Chemistry, 69*, 419–
648 431.

649 Steffen, C., Flueckiger, E., Bosset, J. O., & Ruegg, M. (1987). Swiss – type varieties. In P. F.
650 Fox (Ed), *Cheese: Chemistry, Physics and Microbiology-Major Cheese Groups, Vol. 2*
651 (pp. 93-120). London: Elsevier Applied Science.

652 Stumbo, C. R. (1973). *Thermobacteriology in Food Processing*. London: Academic Press.

653 Su, Y-C., & Ingham, S. C. (2000) Influence of milk centrifugation, brining and ripening
654 conditions in preventing gas formation by *Clostridium* spp. in Gouda cheese. *International*
655 *Journal of Food Microbiology*, 54, 147–154.

656 Szczesniak, A. S. (1986). Sensory texture evaluation methodology. *Reciprocal Meat Conference*
657 *Proceedings*, 39, 86-96.

658 Thayer, D. W., & Boyd, G. (1992). Gamma ray processing to destroy *Staphylococcus aureus* in
659 mechanically deboned chicken meat. *Journal of Food Science*, 57, 848-851.

660 Tsiotsias, A., Savvaidis, I., Vassila, A., Kontominas, M., & Kotzekidou, P. (2002). Control of
661 *Listeria monocytogenes* by low-dose irradiation in combination with refrigeration in the
662 soft whey cheese ‘Anthotyros’. *Food Microbiology*, 19, 117–126.

663 Vissers, M. M. M., Driehuis, F., Te Giffel, M. C., De Jong, P., & Lankveld, J. M. G. (2007).
664 Minimizing the level of Butyric Acid Bacteria spores in farm tank milk. *Journal of Dairy*
665 *Science*, 90, 3278-3285.

666 Vries, Tj., & Stadhouders, J. (1977). Butyric acid bacteria in milk. *Zuivelzicht*, 69, 196-199.

667 Waes, G., & Van Heddeghem, A. (1990). Prevention of butyric acid fermentation by bacterial
668 centrifugation of the cheese milk. *Bulletin International Dairy Federation*, 251, 47-50.

669 Yüceer, S., & Gündüz, G. (1980). Preservation of cheese and pain yogurt by low-dose
670 irradiation. *Journal of Food Protection*, 43, 114-118.

671

672

673 **Figure captions**

674

675

676 Figure 1. Survival curve of *Clostridium tyrobutyricum* in cheese slices subjected to E-
677 beam radiation.

678

679

680 Figure 2. Survival curve of non-sporeforming microbiota of cheese slices subjected to
681 E-beam radiation.

682

683 Figure 3. Total Viable Counts of control (diamonds) and irradiated cheese slices at 1
684 (squares), 2 (triangles) and 3 kGy (circles) stored at 4 °C (full symbols) and 14 °C
685 (empty symbols).

686

687 Figure 4. Effect of radiation treatment (kGy) on the hardness and cohesiveness of the
688 vacuum-packaged cheese slices.

689

690

691 a, b: columns with a different letter are significantly different ($P < 0.05$).

692

693 Figure 5. Response surface plots showing the effect of irradiation treatment (kGy) and
694 the storage time at 4 °C (days) on the colour parameters [a^* (redness), b^* (yellowness)
695 and L^* (lightness)] of the vacuum-packaged cheese slices.

696

697

698 Figure 6. Response surface plots showing the effect of irradiation treatment (kGy) and
699 the storage time at 4 °C (days) on the preference sensory evaluation of the vacuum-
700 packaged irradiated cheese slices.

701

702

703

704 ¹Sum of ranks = [(N1 x 1) + (N2 x 2) + (N3 x 3) + (N4 x 4)]

705 where, N1, N2, N3 or N4 = number of panellists that ranked the sample in the position
706 1 (minimum preference), 2, 3 or 4 (maximum preference) in the rank order test.

707 Critical values of the difference between rank sums ($p < 0.01$) for 20 panellists and 4
708 samples is 25 (according to Chistensen et al., 2006).

709

Table 1 Sensory characteristics of untreated and irradiated cheese slices that showed significant differences ($P < 0.05$) in the triangular test

DOSE (kGy)	0	1	2	3
0		A _{1,2,3}	A _{1,2,3} ; O _{2,3}	A _{1,2,3} ; O _{1,2,3} ; F _{1,2,3}
1				A _{1,2,3} ; O _{1,2,3} ; F _{1,2,3}
2				
3				

A, O, F: Significant differences ($P < 0.05$) for appearance, odour and flavour respectively.

1, 2, 3: The triangle test were carried out on the first day after treatment (0-1st days), during the second (12-13th days) and third week (26-27th days) of storage at 4 °C, respectively.

Figure 1.

Figure 2.

Figure 3.

Figure 4

Figure 5

Figure 6